

NOTES

TABLE 2—I. R. DATA OF METAL COMPLEXES OF N-PHENYL-N'-p-BROMOPHENYL THIOUREA

Sl. No.	Compound	ν NH	δ NH	NH ₂ rocking	ν N-C-N (B ₁)	ν N-C=S (1)	ν N-C=S (2)	ν C=S	ν OAc/ ν NO ₂
1.	L	3200m	1600w	1100m	1540s	1250m	1020m	775m	—
2.	CuL ₂ NO ₂	3225m	1605w	1100w	1555m	1230w	1015w	720w	1380s
3.	CuLOAc	3300b 3220b	1640w	1100m	1580w	1200vw	980vw	705vw	1670b
4.	CuLCl	3350vw 3200w	1600w	1115m	1565w	1220vw	1015w	725w	—
5.	CuL ₂ Cl	3250b 3200b	1600w	1105w	1560m	1225w	1015w	740vw	—
6.	CuL ₂ Br	3350w 3200b	1640vw	1100w	1555w	1225vw	1015vw	725vw	—
7.	CuL ₂ I	3350vw 3200m	1600m	1105m	1560m	1220w	1015w	740vw	—
8.	CuL ₂ Cl	3250b 3200b	1605m	1105m	1560m	1235w	1020w	745w	—
9.	NiL ₂ Cl ₂	3200m	1600w	1095m	1550s	1240w	1010w	760w	—
10.	NiL ₂ Br ₂	3210m	1600w	1105m	1545s	1215w	1010w	760m	—
11.	NiL ₂ I ₂	3210m	1600w	1105m	1550m	1240w	1015w	765w	—

Note: w=weak, vw=very weak, m=medium, s=strong b=broad.

the N-H stretching vibration and 1600 cm⁻¹ corresponds to the N-H bending vibration.

In all the complexes examined, there are considerable lowering in the ν N-C=S (1), ν N-C=S (2) and ν C=S bands due to decrease in double bond character of the sulphur to carbon bond and enhanced doubled bond character of the nitrogen to carbon bond. Further, the shift to higher frequency region of the ν N-C-N(B₁) at 1540 cm⁻¹ indicating metal sulphur bonding (see Table 2).

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Polarographic Studies of In⁺³ Complexes with Thiodiacetic Acid and Iminodiacetic Acid in Aqueous and Aquo-Non-Aqueous Media

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THE dicarboxylic acids having one more coordinating site -N- or -S- atom, other than carboxylic ends have been distinguished as good chelating agents. Various papers¹⁻⁴ have been published on In⁺³ complexes of dicarboxylic acids containing S, N and O atom. In the present communication the

polarographic behaviour of In^{+3} complexes with thiodiacetic acid (TDA) and iminodiacetic acid (IDA) have been reported in aqueous and aquo-non-aqueous media at 25°.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of AR grade. Gelatin (0.005%) was used as maxima suppressor. Final ionic strength ($\mu=0.2M$) of the solutions was adjusted with KNO_3 . The experimental technique is the same as already described⁵.

The dropping mercury electrode had the following characteristics: $m=2.3$ mg/sec., $t=3.0$ sec. (in 0.2M KNO_3 at 1.00 V vs S.C.E.).

The IR drop correction was applied, for this purpose the L.P. Conducscope was utilized.

Results and Discussion

The reduction of In^{+3} -TDA and -IDA complexes in aqueous and aquo-non-aqueous media produced a well defined wave. A diffusion-controlled and reversible reduction is revealed by the constant values of $\text{id}/h^{\frac{1}{2}}$ and slopes (21 ± 2 mV) of plots $\log i/(i_{d-1})$ vs $E_{d.e.}$ at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

In^{+3} - TDA System :

During the pH range 1.5. to 6.8, the half-wave potential of solutions containing $5 \times 10^{-4}M$, 0.15M KNO_3 , 0.05M TDA and gelatin 0.005%, produced cathodic shift in half-wave potential. Plot of $-E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ vs pH indicates two breaks at pH 3.4 and 5.6, and curve remains unaffected below pH 3.4. Further, study of complexation have been carried out at pH 6.3.

The cathodic shift in $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ with increasing concentration [0.0 to 0.1 M] of TDA indicate the formation of the complexes. The plot of $-E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ vs $-\log$ of free ligand concentration [TDA] shows a smooth curve indicating the stepwise complex formation. Therefore, the method of DeFord and Hume⁶ as improved by Irving⁷ was applied to calculate the values of stability constant in aqueous and aquo-non-aqueous (20% each, DMF/DMSO) media. The plot of F_s (TDA) vs [TDA] is a straight line parallel to [TDA]-axis indicates the two complex species are formed with metal-ligand ratio, 1 : 1 and 1 : 2. The values of free ligand concentration of TDA have been calculated by considering the pK_1 (3.26) and pK_2 (5.73) of TDA⁸. The results are summarised in Table 1. The electrode reaction may be represented as follows :

TABLE 1—THE LOG VALUES OF OVERALL STABILITY CONSTANTS IN AQUEOUS AND AQUO-NON-AQUEOUS MEDIA

System	Medium	$\log \beta_1$	$\log \beta_2$
In(III)-TDA	Aqueous	3.26	5.73
	20% DMSO	3.83	6.19
	20% DMF	3.95	6.28
In(III)-IDA	Aqueous	6.45	11.61
	20% DMSO	7.03	12.85
	20% DMF	7.15	13.13

In^{+3} - IDA System :

The irreversibility of In (III)-IDA complexes between the pH 9.2 to 10.6 has been reported⁹. But this system was found to be quasireversible in the pH range 7.5 to 8.9 and reversible in the pH range 2.5 to 7.0. The plot of $-E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ vs pH shows that as pH increases from 2.5 to 7.0, a cathodic shift in $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ is observed. Thus complexation studies have been carried out at pH 6.2.

The cathodic shift in $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ on increasing IDA (0.0 to 0.08M) shows the formation of the complexes. The plot of $-E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ vs $-\log$ of free ligand concentration [IDA] shows a smooth curve indicating the stepwise complex formation. Therefore, the method of DeFord and Hume⁶ as improved by Irving⁷ was applied to compute the values of overall stability constant in aqueous and aquo-non-aqueous (20% each, DMF/DMSO) media. The values of free ligand concentration [IDA] have been calculated by considering the pK_1 (2.54) and pK_2 (9.12) of IDA¹⁰. The two complex species are observed with metal-ligand ratios 1 : 1 and 1 : 2. The results are summarised in Table 1.

The electrode reaction may be represented as follows :

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Complexes of Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Fe(III) and Os(IV) with 4-*p*-Dimethylamino-Anilino-3-Penten-2-One

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A large number of β -ketoimines¹⁻⁵ are known. They act as bidentate ligands and serve as very good chelating agents. Numerous transition metal complexes of β -ketoimines have been studied by various workers⁶⁻⁹. This communication deals with complexes of Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Fe(III) and Os(IV) ions with a bidentate Schiff's base derived from *p*-dimethylamino-aniline and acetyl acetone, known as 4-*p*-Dimethylamino-Anilino-3-penten-2-One (DIMAPO).

Experimental

All chemicals and reagents used were of A. R. grade.

Preparation of 4-*p*-Dimethylamino-Anilino-3-penten-2-One :

This was formed by condensing an ethereal soln. of *p*-dimethylamino-aniline and freshly distilled acetyl acetone on water bath (45°-50°) and evaporating off ether. The amine was prepared from *p*-nitroso dimethyl aniline¹⁰ and the latter was obtained from dimethyl aniline¹¹.

Preparation and Isolation of Complexes :

Bis-[4-*p*-Dimethylamino-Anilino-3-penten-2-One]-copper(II), *Diaquo bis*-[4-*p*-Dimethylamino-Anilino-3-penten-2-One]-Ni(II) and Co(II) - 20 ml of 0.1M solutions of the metal chloride in 95% ethanol were treated with the ligand. The pH of the soln. was raised by addition of aq. ammonia(2N). The black (Cu), sky blue (Ni) and buff grey (Co) precipitates formed after filtering, washing with water and a little ethanol, were dried. The complexes are slightly soluble in common organic solvents. The copper and cobalt complexes do not melt, the nickel complex melts at 208°. Formula :

[Cu(C₁₃H₁₇N₂O)₂] Anal. calcd : Cu : 12.77%, C : 62.70%, H : 6.83% and N : 11.21%, Found : Cu : 12.60%, C : 62.56%, H : 6.90% and N : 11.32%. [Ni(C₁₃H₁₇N₂O)₂·(H₂O)₂] Anal. calcd : Ni : 11.11%, C : 58.76%, H : 7.53%, N : 10.54%, Found : Ni : 10.94%, C : 58.58%, H : 7.68%, N : 10.32%.

[Co(C₁₃H₁₇N₂O)₂·(H₂O)₂] Anal. calcd : Co : 11.14%, C : 58.98%, H : 7.18%, N : 10.59%, Found : Co : 10.89%, C : 58.68%, H : 6.98%, N : 10.30%.

Tris-[4-*p*-Dimethylamino-Anilino-3-penten-2-One]-Fe(III) - 40 ml of 0.1M soln. of anhydrous ferric chloride in 95% ethanol was treated with the ligand. An intense brown colour was formed. The soln. was concentrated on a water bath and cooled. A brown precipitate was formed by the addition of a little 0.1 M aq. sodium hydroxide soln. It was filtered, washed with distilled water, dried and recrystallized from ethanol. m.p. 110°. It is soluble in absolute alcohol, acetone and benzene. Formula : [Fe(C₁₃H₁₇N₂O)₃] Anal. calcd : Fe : 7.9%, C : 66.21%, H : 7.21%, N : 11.88%. Found : Fe : 7.82%, C : 66.40%, H : 7.01%, N : 11.72%.

Tetra Kis-[4-*p*-Dimethylamino-Anilino-3-penten-2-One]-Os(IV) dihydrate - The grey crystalline precipitate was formed by refluxing osmium tetrachloride soln. with the ligand in the ratio 1 : 4 (M : L) and 3-4 ml of aqueous dil. ammonia soln. for 1½ hr and subsequent cooling. The precipitate was filtered, washed with distilled water and a little acetone and dried in vacuum over anhydrous P₂O₅; m.p. above 300°. The complex compound is slightly soluble in acetone and absolute alcohol. Formula : [Os(C₁₃H₁₇N₂O)₄]·2H₂O Anal. calcd : Os : 17.38%, C : 56.78%, H : 6.91%, N : 10.19%. Found : Os : 17.18%, C : 56.56%, H : 6.80%, N : 9.98%.

Results and Discussion

Cu(L)₂ : The electronic spectrum of the copper complex, Cu(L)₂ (L = DIMAPO), is consistent with an essentially tetrahedral structure. The d-d bands for a planar structure occur in the range 14000-18000 cm⁻¹, whereas tetrahedral complexes possess a broad band in the region 15000 cm⁻¹ and a strong

* For Correspondence.